

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Nathoo****FIRST NAME: Rishma****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%.

The author used the following software: MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11.

List your seven key concepts with the page number in the text below:

1. Purpose of academic essays (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7) Comparison between academic and non-academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024; Parker 2020)
2. Writing structure and style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24) Punctuation and grammar (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 32-57)
3. Ethics in writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34)

ACADEMIC WRITING IS COMPLICATED

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing informs, educates, and promotes learning on a topic. Academic papers use facts to anchor in perspective based on information – observable and interpretative or factual and assumed to be ‘matter of fact’ – to aid in understanding a topic and ultimately create meaning. This seems simple; however, reflecting on the reading for the ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack for Period 1, I found that academic writing is complex, sometimes counterintuitive, and time-consuming. The complexity comes from expansive and detailed punctuation, grammar, and citation rules. Writing styles and structures consistently portray information, reducing manual efforts. However, several styles can be adopted, with some being more appropriate to a particular type of academic writing than others, requiring additional manual effort to ‘get it right.’ Academic writing is formal. The writing and vocabulary are not meant for the mass public; thus, when read by the public, they can be unclear, difficult to digest, and unnatural. It becomes challenging to decipher critical messages, especially when the focus turns from analyzing concepts and findings to defining terms, building their vocabulary, or wondering what the author intends to convey.

This response paper explores five topics, showing how confusing academic writing can be. These topics include the purpose of scholarly essays, the comparison between

academic and non-academic writing, writing structure and style, punctuation and grammar, and ethics in writing. I chose these topics as they are the essence of the material for the ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack, Period 1, and avoid copying the exact wording of the chapters.

2) PURPOSE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Academic writing's roots are in facts (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). Its purpose is to express a position, a point of view, or an argument worthy of discovery using a logical flow of facts. However, the description of an academic essay from ESSAYPRO.com implies that non-fictional content used to express ideas, like stories and examples, can be mixed in. "Essays are versatile expressions of ideas. Descriptive essays vividly portray subjects, narratives share personal stories, expository essays convey information, and persuasive essays aim to influence opinions" (Parker 2020). From this lens, an academic essay is no different from any other information product that references and analyzes facts to validate or discredit a position or point of view.

Confusion further arises when Sheridan College's website identifies four types of essays: "expository, argumentative or persuasive, reflective and descriptive" (Sheridan Library, n.d.). For example, a reflective essay, which includes communicating personal experiences, is no different from a thought-leadership piece produced in the business environment. A descriptive essay encourages subjective writing. However, readers can scrutinize subjective writing because it lacks significant supporting data points. The role of a hypothesis in a descriptive essay needs to be clarified, and the incorporation of factual data, though it can imply the subjective nature of the essay, is not required. Hence, I am surprised that EUCLID conveys the factual aspects of academic writing rather than the subjectivity embedded within it. Subject matter or industry aside, I wonder why academic essays cannot be limited to one or two types. xxx

3) COMPARISON BETWEEN ACADEMIC AND NON-ACADEMIC WRITING

According to the website ESSAYPRO.com, there are seven types of academic writing compared to three broad non-academic writing (Parker 2020).

Table 1: Comparing Academic vs. Non-Academic Writing

Types of Academic Writing	Types of Non-Academic Writing
1. Expository	1. Articles (e.g., magazines, news pieces)
2. Persuasive	2. Books (e.g., novels, memoirs, poetry, self-help)
3. Descriptive	3. Social media posts (e.g., websites, tweets)
4. Narrative	
5. Analytical	

Types of Academic Writing	Types of Non-Academic Writing
6. Research Papers	
7. Literature Reviews	

A few things stood out when comparing the two columns in the table above. For example, storytelling is a common denominator across narrative academic writing and books. The reference to facts *may* distinguish them, though they can be part of both writing types. The similarity creates a new question on how many factual data points are required for a writing piece to be considered academic. Similarly, articles and research papers both aim to present and research information, as does an expository writing piece. Though there are other examples, these two highlight the complexity inherent in academic writing. I am surprised that educational institutions, which lead to many discoveries and insights, make writing and understanding academic writing pieces more complicated and separate from day-to-day writing than necessary.

4) WRITING STRUCTURE AND STYLE

I agree that writing structure and style is essential. All writing adopts a structure and style. The absence of either or both components challenges a reader's ability to follow and comprehend the presented information. Both academic and non-academic writing offer a similar structure. Minus a summary or hypothesis, as they are not always present in non-academic writing, information is introduced under headings or chapters, then elaborated with details, analysis, and analogies or case studies, and then concludes with the main point, reinforcing the introduction. Font type, spelling, writing voice, and inclusion of symbols, among other style features, are present. Yet, despite the strong commonality, academic writing is viewed and discussed as drastically different than any other type of writing. The difference appears to be minimal when agreeing on the importance of representing facts structurally.

Style also varies among the different writing forms. Academic writing is formal, whereas non-academic writing can be formal or informal (McKowan 2024). Generalizations, assumptions, and exaggerations are kept to a minimum if included at all in academic writing. According to one source, personalization or subjectivity is meant for mass readership, while academic writing has a selective audience. However, I do not believe this is necessarily true. Earlier in this paper, it was noted that some academic essays and writing intentionally include stories and provide vivid descriptions of situations to communicate, examine, and present information. If academic writings explain, inform, present, analyze, and assess information using varied tactics such as stories, scenarios, or investigative processes, why are they called out 'different' from writings for mass publication? ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack, Period 1 notes that style and style guides enforce a consistent writing style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24). While that is true, consistent writing is not without purpose. The goal of any writing is to engage and create comprehension. I do not believe that academic writing demands a unique, standardized

structure and style. Academic writing can gain higher traction, readership, and validity if the language used can be easily digested. That requires reorienting the writing style for both academics and the mass public. Having one global standard that is simple, easy to apply, and offers limited leeway to accommodate ‘an exception’ or ‘unique purpose’ of one type of writing over another would reduce the confusion on when to use what style and remove the need to have voluminous books and guides on writing style.

5) PUNCTUATION AND GRAMMAR

Three chapters in the ACA-401D Course pack for Period 1 focus on punctuation and grammar (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-32). A section on the Chicago Manual Style also summarizes critical elements for academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 43-57). Working through over thirty pages of information on what and how to write is overwhelming. Separating the information in different chapters means a student needs to toggle back and forth to ensure consistency between the chapters or choose which data to follow when in doubt. In such structures, my comprehension needs to be improved and supported. Technology tools like Grammarly and Zotero can reduce the risk of writing inconsistently or incorrectly according to EUCLID guidelines. If EUCLID trusts these tools, abbreviating the content on punctuation and grammar with links to a quick reference guide or checklist to aid student learning will ensure clarity. I want to rely on these tools, allowing me to focus more on education and analysis. I can appreciate the need to learn the technicalities involved in academic writing. Still, in a world where technology is leveraged to remove some of the route elements of an activity, technology can be beneficial in allowing scholarly writers to focus on content.

6) ETHICS IN WRITING

As expressed in earlier sections, the foundation of academic writing is facts. The idea of attributing information, not plagiarizing, is clear. Instead, it is ethical and illustrates transparency and accountability to the author’s integrity, the writing process, and the piece. The confusion stems from when to cite. For example, the ACA-401D Course pack for Period 1 states that using someone else’s ideas without citation is plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). However, unless academic writing is solely based on the author’s research, without reference to any ‘outside’ information, a significant portion of the paper (minus personal insights, which are meant to be kept to a minimum) will be cited. For example, when using external information sources, academic writing becomes an exercise of mixing and parsing relevant information through paraphrasing. Analysis, an author’s point of view, becomes the only piece not cited. However, the analysis is rooted in secondary material. I could argue that it, too, needs to be mentioned. Citation can be complicated. Bibliographies are an excellent way to acknowledge all the sources that have directly and indirectly influenced the academic writing piece.

7) CONCLUSION

Writing is a form of communication, information gathering, and learning tool. Writing aims to inform, engage, and communicate. Academic writing can challenge comprehension, and non-academic writing can spur non-fictional thinking. Approximately 65 pages of the ACA-401D Course pack for Period 1 aim to specify the uniqueness of academic writing. When reading the information, much of the information is like non-academic writing minus the complexity brought on through different academic essay types, writing structures and styles, punctuations and grammar, really thinking through the ethical consideration of what is uniquely self-written and thought of vs. what information stems from another author's writing.

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